

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

ADDRESSING THE INTERSECTION OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING AND DRUG TRAFFICKING: INITIAL CONSIDERATIONS ON INTERAGENCY COOPERATION SCALE.

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POLICY STATEMENT

Drug trafficking and human trafficking are serious crimes with severe social and legal consequences worldwide. While the former generally involves the illegal production, distribution, sale, and transport of controlled substances, the latter entails the subjugation of human beings for commercial purposes, such as forced labor, sexual exploitation, and debt bondage, among other forms of abuse. When these two crimes intersect, a significant challenge arises for law enforcement: Can individuals who have been trafficked and are forced into serving as drug mules, knowingly or unknowingly, be convicted for drug trafficking? Is it possible to be both a victim and a criminal simultaneously? Governments and international organizations are actively working to prevent and combat these crimes, as well as to support victims and raise awareness on these issues. In that way, this paper aims to shed light on the subject, sharing challenges faced and recommendations for governmental and intergovernmental agencies and all stakeholders focused on this issue.

BACKGROUND

Human trafficking and drug trafficking are pressing global issues that frequently intertwine. At this intersection, among other profiles, we find trafficked individuals who, knowingly or unknowingly, become involved in drug transport, thus simultaneously being victims and offenders. This policy brief aims to share challenges faced by the Brazilian justice system in identifying drug mules who are victims of human trafficking and to provide recommendations to address this complex issue. For this purpose, we have reviewed a study by the UNODC Liaison and Partnership Office in Brazil (LPOBRA), in partnership with the Ministry of Justice and Public Safety (MJSP), supported by the Government of Sweden through UNODC's Global Programme against Trafficking in Persons (GLOT59), implemented by the Human Trafficking and Migrant Smuggling Section (HTMSS). (UNODOC/LPOBRA et al., 2022). This study, published in 2023, examined 105 verdicts from a Federal Court in Guarulhos (São Paulo) between 2018 and 2019, focusing on drug mules who were victims of human trafficking and foreign women imprisoned for drug transport. The Instituto Terra, Trabalho e Cidadania (ITTC) provided testimonies about these imprisoned foreign women.

FINDINGS

Human trafficking and drug trafficking are severe crimes with significant impacts on societies globally. Human trafficking involves exploiting individuals through recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt using threat, force, coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, abuse of power or vulnerability, or by giving or receiving payments to obtain the consent of a person having control over another for exploitation purposes. Exploitation might entail forced labor, servitude, slavery, sexual exploitation, and organ removal, among other abuses.

Drug trafficking is the illicit trade of psychoactive substances like cocaine, marijuana, heroin, and methamphetamines, produced, transported, and distributed illegally worldwide. Drug trafficking networks operate globally, moving vast quantities of illegal drugs across borders and continents, feeding a growing consumer demand, and funding large-scale criminal activities.

In these networks, traffickers coerce, deceive, or force trafficked individuals to transport drugs across international borders (drug mules), creating an intersection between human trafficking and drug trafficking. These human trafficking victims often face vulnerabilities like poverty, unemployment, and lack of essential services, making them easy targets for traffickers who recruit and exploit them. In that case, are they victims (trafficked victims) or criminals (drug dealers)?

The situation for trafficked mules is complex as they are simultaneously human trafficking victims and accused of drug trafficking crimes. The justice system often inadequately addresses or acknowledges their vulnerabilities, leading to a lack of proper protection and support. For instance, Brazilian legislation does not explicitly cover "committing any form of servitude" in its definition of human trafficking, further complicating the identification of trafficked individuals coerced into drug transport.

The analysis of verdicts uncovered cases where drug mules acted under coercion or deception, potentially qualifying them as human trafficking victims. However, since Brazilian legislation does not explicitly recognize the possibility of coerced drug trafficking by trafficked individuals, authorities did not recognize their victim status. Because of this legal gap, authorities consistently used confessions about drug transport as evidence of criminal intent and convicted many, even though traffickers might have trafficked some of these convicts.

CONCLUSIONS

Addressing the intersection between human and drug trafficking is vital to protecting the rights of vulnerable individuals ensnared in these criminal networks. Given the insights shared in this policy brief, it is prudent to champion the implementation of appropriate global measures, like the recommendations mentioned above, to recognize trafficked victims and differentiate their cases from regular drug trafficking. This mature stance promotes both justice and human rights worldwide. Lastly, we suggest policymakers and other stakeholders cooperate to ensure a fair and humane response to this issue affecting many societies around the globe.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, we propose the following recommendations:

- (I) Extend the study to other regions of Brazil and globally, including border areas, to comprehensively understand drug mules potentially being human trafficking victims;
- (II) Provide training for agencies and professionals on the topic, equipping them to structure defenses and studies pointing to coercion, fraud, or deception used by traffickers, challenging automatic assumptions of criminal intent;
- (III) Develop training programs for justice system actors to identify human trafficking victims better and differentiate their cases from regular drug trafficking;
- (IV) Conduct comprehensive assessments in prisons studying profiles of mules convicted for drug transport, focusing on recurring indicators of victimization by human trafficking;
- (V) Consider including "committing any form of servitude" as a premise related to human trafficking, paving the way to recognize the intersection between human and drug trafficking, not just in Brazilian legislation but in any global society facing this challenge.

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